

COMMON PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN TRANSLATION

¹Saloxitdinova Ruxshona Sur'atjon qizi, ²Xodjayeva S.S.

¹Student of the 1st course of the Faculty of Translation, UzSWLU

²Scientific advisor

Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to examine the distinctive characteristics of medical text translation. It will include studying the unique traits of informative translation, "false friends of translation" in medical manuscripts, 'lexical groups,' and sets of abbreviations related to the realm of medical translation.*

Keywords: *translation, terminology, scientific, medical, problem, lexical, understanding, text, word, science, terms, phrases.*

Аннотация. *Цель данной статьи – рассмотреть отличительные особенности перевода медицинских текстов. Он будет включать изучение уникальных особенностей информативного перевода, «ложных друзей перевода» в медицинских рукописях, «лексических групп» и наборов сокращений, связанных с областью медицинского перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, терминология, научный, медицинский, проблемный, лексический, понимание, текст, слово, наука, термины, фразы.*

Аннотация. *Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi tibbiy matnlarni tarjima qilishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqishdir. Unda ma'lumotli tarjimaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, tibbiy qo'lyozmalardagi "tarjimaning soxta do'stlari", "leksik to'plamlar" va tibbiy tarjima sohasi bilan bog'liq qisqartmalar to'plamini o'rganish kiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tarjima, terminologiya, ilmiy, tibbiy, muammo, leksik, tushunish, matn, so'z, ilm-fan, terminlar, frazalar.*

In today's world, our surroundings are full with science, so that, translation is an essential, troublesome and undertaking process, and this action requires deep comprehension which translators most commonly come across and do not understand the meaning of text. Dr. Miremadi divided the problem into two main categories: lexical problems and syntactic problems ("Theory and practice of translation" – M.T. Iriskulov – p 31.).

Technical, scientific, legal and medical fields often have complex terminology that requires translators with specialized knowledge. Precision is crucial in these contexts to avoid errors that could have serious consequences. That's why translator should know the academic and scientific terms and phrases, the meanings of ordinary words while they come with terms in this process. Not being aware of that kind of words or not understanding the academic text will cause the lexical problem in translation. Besides, a translator of medical texts must be clearly focused on the topic, be able to reliably identify ambiguous terms and expressions (not forgetting the existence of "false friends of the translator") and correctly determine their interpretation.

One aspect of using medical terminology is fluency in the topographical symbols, planes and axes used to describe morphology, as well as knowledge of the International Anatomical Nomenclature. Medical translation, particularly in specialized fields like dentistry, requires a deep understanding of both the subject matter and the linguistic nuances involved.

I did a research on medical texts and find some examples depend on dentistry. **What are the wisdom teeth?**

Wisdom teeth are upper and lower third molars, located at the very back of the mouth. They are called wisdom teeth because usually they come in when a person is between age 17 and 21 or older enough to have gained some “wisdom”.

In the text, underlined word **come in** means *to enter somewhere*. If we translate that sentence such as:

Ular aql tishi deb atalishlariga sabab, bu tishlar, odatda, inson 17 va 21 yosh oralig’ida bo’lganda yoki aql kiradigan darajada yetarlicha ulga’yganda kiradi.

There is fault in translation, because if it is translated like that, people may come across misunderstanding the text. Instead of translating the word “come in” – kirmoq, it’s better to say “chiqmoq”. There is appropriate translation of this sentence: Ular aql tishi deb atalishlariga sabab, bu tishlar odatda inson 17 va 21 yosh oralig’ida bo’lganda yoki aql kiradigan darajada yetarlicha ulga’yganda chiqadi. We chose the word “chiqmoq” instead of “kirmoq”. The reason for this, teeth do not enter somewhere, they are in our mouth, but they come up breaking partway through gums.

Another example which explored for translating terms in the text is that:

Experts say that healthy coping strategies can help reduce the risk of gum problems getting worse. **Healthy coping strategy’s** literal translation is – sog’lom ko’chirish tamoyillari/strategiyalari. But it is not true translation, because it means behaviors that can set you up for success. Sometimes translation requires to adapt to the target text or find equivalences of phrases in target language. So while we translating this sentence, we use the adaptation method of translation to give better version. Translation of this, be like that: *Ekspertlar sog’lom turmush tarziga rioya qilish milk bilan bog’liq muammolarni yomonlashish xavfini kamaytirishini aytishdi.*

Effective translation goes beyond words; it requires understanding cultural nuances, idioms, and context. Failing to capture these subtleties can lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations. Translators must be well-versed in both languages and cultural contexts to ensure accurate communication. Even the best translations can fail when trying to interpret phrases and concepts that have no underlying cultural equivalent.

Although the terms used are supposed to indicate clear meaning, some of these expressions can become problematic when translating them. In medicine, it's important to be careful with certain words that can be confusing because they might cause mistakes in treatment that could be really bad. Here are some examples of medical false friends you may have faced:

In the EDQM glossary, a “soft capsule” in English - “Capsule molle” in French. However, a “hard capsule” translated into French like “Gélule”.

There are some examples of medical false friends in German.

German term	False friend in English	Possible English translation
Ambulanz	Ambulance	outpatient department
Dose	Dose	can, tin
Expertise	expertise	report (by experts)
Gift	Gift	Poison

These misunderstandings in casual settings could result in little more than an odd glance. However, a mistake like this could make a crucial translation in medicine meaningless. Because of this, accurate translations necessitate skilled translators working in their native tongues, particularly when patient safety is at stake. For instance, in Spanish, the word *embarazada* is the false friend of the English word *embarrassed*, but the Spanish word does not give the meaning like in English, it means *pregnant*.

Although there are differences across individuals, nations, and specializations when it comes to medical acronyms, these are some of the most widely used ones among medical

professionals worldwide. These ought to make it easier for you to understand doctor's notes and other medical records. The rapid emergence of medical abbreviations in contemporary English is demonstrated by the use of abbreviations that are not listed in dictionaries. Therefore, the primary issue with translating medical acronyms is that, depending on the illness, anatomy, or operation being described, the same abbreviations may have different meanings.

The purpose of the paper is to examine both nationally and generally relevant aspects of English medical abbreviations, to investigate the extralinguistic and interlinguistic conditions that led to their creation, to identify patterns in the use of medical abbreviations in contemporary English, and to examine the peculiarities in the categorization of abbreviations.

A particular focus was also placed on looking into some fundamental processes that could be used to translate them. Examples of medical abbreviations: *AIDS – Acquired immune deficiency syndrome* – in Uzbek it is translated as *OITS – Orttilgan immune tanqisligi sindromi*.

While translating this abbreviation, we use the literal translation method. *CVA - Cerebrovascular accident* – in Uzbek it translated *insult*. The most common way to communicate foreign acronyms is the transference of the foreign acronym with its corresponding acronym.

In conclusion, knowing medical terminology is effective communication, accuracy in diagnosis, and teaching and training health care staff. Overall, lexico-semantic features of medical terminology among translators of both source and target languages requires in-depth knowledge and thorough knowledge of medical concepts and terminology. This is necessary to ensure accurate and culturally sensitive translations in the medical field. Therefore, translators should know the pivotal role of translation in a multilingual society. Thus, using different methods while translating, understanding the main meaning of a context, knowing cultural borders and differences, and being aware of phraseological units in both the source and target language are the main aspects of translation. Having knowledge and experience prevents misunderstandings that appear during the translation process and promotes opening the language's real capability.

REFERENCES

1. "Theory and practice of translation" – M.T. Iriskulov, N.M. Kambarov, K.D. Tukhtaeva. Tashkent – 2020.
2. "Translation of Terminology" – I.M. Tuxtasinov, G.P. Kurbanazarova, S.N. Sultanova – "Yangi asr avlodi" – Toshkent – 2020.
3. Lejchik, V.M. terminology: object, structure. Moscow, 2012
4. <https://globaltranslations.com.br>
5. <https://www.linkedin.com>
6. <https://biglanguage.com>
7. <https://www.naargmedia.com>
8. biglanguage.com
9. www.abbreviations.com
10. oceantranslation.com